

Acidoid Behaviour of Charcoal as a Function of its Oxygen Complexes. Part VI. Adsorption of Ammonia

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The interaction of charcoal and ammonia in solution or gaseous phase appears to involve two distinct and dissimilar reactions. The first one is a neutralising reaction involving the acidic CO_2 -complex in the charcoal. The magnitude of this reaction depends on the condition of the experiment. The ammonia adsorbed can be recovered completely on hydrolysis with HCl or on boiling with NaOH . The second one involves fixation of nitrogen in a non-hydrolysable form. It appears to be of activated type, but cannot be attributed to any surface group that has been postulated so far.

Adsorption of ammonia by oxygen-containing charcoals and carbon blacks has engaged the attention of a number of investigators in recent years. Anderson and Emmett¹ showed that such carbons could take up nearly three times as much ammonia as expected from their nitrogen surface area. This was attributed to the polarity and capacity of ammonia to form hydrogen bonds with the constituents of the oxygen complex. The heat index value, C , of the B.E.T. equation was also appreciably high and decreased invariably on outgassing the samples. Bente and Walton² and Emmett³ reported formation of stable nitrogen complexes on treatment of charcoal with ammonia and nitric oxide at high temperatures. Hofmann and Ohlerich⁴ as well as Boehm *et al.*⁵ studied the reaction between dry ammonia and a sugar charcoal, pretreated with a mixture of sulphuric acid and nitric acid and containing 16% oxygen, in the temperature range of 110° to 410° . An appreciable amount of ammonia, as indicated by the nitrogen content of the charcoal, was fixed and the value increased with the temperature. They suggested that the interaction involved substitution of surface hydroxyl groups by amino groups. But, on the other hand, only a small amount of hydrochloric acid was neutralised by these samples. Moreover, Studebaker⁶ has shown that nitrogen in a carbon black, treated with ammonia, is stable to hydrolysis and the product exhibits only a slight van Slyke reaction. The mechanism of the interaction of ammonia and carbons is therefore by no means properly understood. As the possibility of fixation of nitrogen by charcoal on treatment with aqueous ammonia has not been studied and the exact role of surface-oxygen complexes on the course and magnitude of the reaction with aqueous or dry ammonia has not been properly elucidated, the present work has been undertaken.

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 756.

2. *Ibid.*, 1943, 47, 329.

3. *Chem. Rev.*, 1949, 43, 69.

4. *Angew. Chem.*, 1950, 62, 16.

5. Proc. Third Carbon Conference, 1957, Buffalo University, Pergamon Press, 1958, 1, 241.

6. *Rubber Age*, 1957, 80, No. 4, 661.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two samples of charcoal, prepared by carbonisation of recrystallised canesugar and coconut shells^{7,8}, were used as such (referred to as 'original' charcoals in the text) as well as after outgassing at 300°, 400°, 500°, 700°, 1000°, and 1100° in the manner described earlier⁷. A portion of each original charcoal was treated with chlorine water to raise its oxygen content⁹. As has already been shown, no chlorine is taken up during this process. The total amount of oxygen and hydrogen evolved as CO₂, CO, H₂O and H₂, on outgassing each sample, was also determined in the manner already described^{7,10}.

Adsorption of Ammonia from Solution Phase.—Several 1 g.-portions of charcoal were mixed with aqueous ammonia (100 ml) of a known concentration in 250 ml pyrex glass bottles and the suspensions shaken mechanically. After a definite interval two of the bottles were withdrawn. An aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid of one was added to a known excess of HCl, which was then back-titrated against a standard alkali solution in the usual way. To the second bottle a known excess of HCl was added, the contents shaken for 2 hr., and the suspension filtered; the charcoal was washed with hot CO₂-free distilled water. The filtrate and the washings were examined for the unneutralised HCl by titrating an aliquot against a standard alkali solution in the usual manner. Similar experiments without charcoal (blanks) and with silica gel 'precipitated from a solution of sodium silicate on addition of an equivalent amount of HCl) and a sample of soil showed that little or no ammonia could remain unaccounted for. The washed charcoal was dried and examined for its nitrogen content by micro-analysis.

Adsorption from Gaseous Phase.—Gaseous ammonia, obtained by warming ammonia liquor and dried by passing over fused calcium oxide, was led (@ 1 litre/hr.) over charcoal (5-10 g.), held in position by asbestos plug in a rotating pyrex glass tube of 3/4" bore which could be heated in a tube furnace to a desired temperature to 400°. After the treatment, the charcoal was allowed to cool gradually to the room temperature in the atmosphere of ammonia and then a part of it (about 1 g., accurately weighed in a closed bottle) was boiled with NaOH and the ammonia liberated was estimated in the usual way. Another part (about 1 g., accurately weighed as before) was mixed with *N*/10-HCl (100 ml) and the suspension shaken for 2 hr. Since charcoal before treatment with ammonia did not consume any significant amount of the acid, the fall in concentration of the acid was taken as a measure of the adsorbed ammonia. The residual charcoal, left after treatment with NaOH and HCl, was examined for its nitrogen content by the micro-analytical technique.

Base-adsorption Capacity.—The maximum base-adsorption capacity (i.e., total acidity) was determined as before^{8,10} by mixing charcoal (1 g.) with 0.2*N*-Ba(OH)₂ (100 ml) or NaOH solution and shaking the suspension for 48 hr.

DISCUSSION

The amounts of ammonia, adsorbed by the original sugar charcoal from aqueous solution (0.0641*N*), after different intervals of time, together with the amounts that can-

7. Puri *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4880.

8. Puri *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 50, 1071.

9. Puri *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1980, 37, 171.

10. Puri *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 758.

not be recovered on treatment with HCl, are recorded in Table I. A steady state appears to set in after about 6 hr. About one third of the total ammonia taken up by the charcoal is not recovered even on treatment with HCl, as confirmed by presence of nearly an equivalent amount of nitrogen in the charcoal, determined by micro-analysis. This indicates the formation of a stable nitrogen complex in charcoal even on treatment with ammonia solution for a short time.

TABLE I

Aq. ammonia added = 100ml of 0.0641*N* = 6.41m.e./g.charcoal.

* A m m o n i a .

Shaking time.	Total adsorbed.	Not recoverable with 0.1 <i>N</i> -HCl.	Nitrogen fixed by charcoal (expressed as equiv. of ammonia).
30 min.	1.70	0.47	0.45
1 hr.	1.80	0.55	..
2	2.01	0.59	..
6	2.12	0.70	0.78
24	2.09	0.72	0.84
48	2.13	0.72	0.82

*Expressed in m. equiv. /g.

TABLE II

A m m o n i a .

*Aq. ammonia added.	Total added.	Not recoverable with 0.1 <i>N</i> -HCl.	Nitrogen fixed by charcoal (expressed as equiv. of ammonia).
5.29	1.91	0.60	0.54
8.84	2.35	0.98	1.10
9.70	2.58	0.96	0.92
20.86	3.47	1.08	1.30
40.00	3.54	1.02	..

*Dissolved in 100 ml soln.

N. B. The values are expressed in m. equiv./g.

The effect of concentration of ammonia solution on the interaction is shown in Table II. It is seen that although there is an increase in the adsorption value with increase in the concentration, the amount of ammonia 'fixed' in a non-hydrolysable form remains more or less the same, independent of the concentration within the range examined. This nitrogen could not be recovered even on boiling the charcoal with NaOH. The fact that a significant, though a small, amount of nitrogen can be fixed so firmly by charcoal even from a dilute aqueous solution of ammonia in a short time suggests that there must be some highly active groups or selective sites on the charcoal surface for this interaction.

Maximum amounts of ammonia adsorbed from the solution phase, using 0.1*N* aqueous solution and extending the time of shaking to 24 hr., by the various samples of charcoal are recorded in Table III. Amounts of NaOH and Ba(OH)₂ neutralised and of CO₂ evolved on high-temperature evacuation in each case are also included in the table.

It is seen that the ammonia values, like NaOH and Ba(OH)₂ values, vary with the CO₂-complex. Unlike the latter values, which are almost equivalent to the amount of CO₂-complex contained in each sample, the ammonia value, even though it is inclusive of the amount fixed in a non-hydrolysable form, is, however, considerably less in every case. This is probably due to the fact that ammonia being a much weaker base cannot push the neutralisation of the complex to completion.

TABLE III

Samples.	CO ₂ evolved on evacuation.	Ba(OH) ₂ neutralised.	NaOH neutralised*.	Ammonia adsorbed from soln. phase.	Ammonia adsorbed from gaseous phase and recovered with HCl. Reactionts.		Nitrogen fixed by charcoal (expressed as equiv. of ammonia).
					Not cooled.	Cooled.	
Sugar charcoal:							
Original	7.25	7.33	7.20	3.54	4.08	6.70	1.58
Treated with Cl ₂ water	11.78	11.86	11.71	5.67	(4.76) 4.84	9.12	2.12
Coconut shell charcoal:							
Original	3.72	3.63	3.67	2.14	3.04 (2.68)	3.48	0.94
Treated with Cl ₂ water	10.60	10.51	10.43	4.65	4.74	8.25	1.64
Sugar charcoal:							
Outgassed at 300°	3.62	3.59	3.53	1.68			
400°	2.06	2.15	2.09	0.98			
500°	0.60	0.66	0.63	0.37			
700°	Nil	Nil	Nil	0.10			
1000°	"	"	"	0.15			
1100°	"	"	"	0.12			

N. B. Figures in column 2 refer to m. equiv./g.

TABLE IV

Treatment.	Ammonia adsorbed and recovered on treatment with HCl.	Nitrogen fixed by charcoal (expressed as equivalents of ammonia).
Room temp.	4.98 m.e./g.	1.58 m.e./g.
200°	3.01	1.94
300°	2.32	2.65
400°	1.79	2.98

Amounts of ammonia adsorbed by the first four samples of charcoal from the gaseous phase at the room temperature, as determined by the recovery of ammonia on treatment with *N*/10-HCl, are included in Table III. The values, obtained on boiling a portion of the treated charcoal with a solution of NaOH, are of the same order (not shown). It is seen that the values, although appreciably higher, are still less than those obtained with the other

alkalies. It was then realised that the heat evolved during neutralisation of the CO_2 -complex by ammonia gas might have caused some local heating of the charcoal so as to raise its temperature sufficiently to cause partial elimination of the complex itself. This view was checked in two ways. Firstly, the CO_2 -complex of two of these samples was re-estimated (after removal of adsorbed ammonia by treatment with HCl) in the usual manner. The values, shown in parentheses are seen to be considerably less than those obtained previously (column 6) and are of the same order as the ammonia values, as expected. Secondly, the ammonia values for all the four samples were determined again by passing a current of iced water in a jacket around the reaction tube so as to offset the thermal effect developed during the process. The results are now seen to be much closer to the total acidity or the CO_2 -complex values. These observations indicate strongly that ammonia adsorption, like adsorption of other alkalies, by charcoal is largely a neutralising reaction due to the acid character of charcoal owing to presence of the CO_2 complex.

An appreciable amount of nitrogen was fixed in these charcoals in non-hydrolysable form, as indicated in the last column of Table III.

The effect of temperature on the interaction is shown in Table IV in the case of original sugar charcoal. Adsorption of ammonia in the hydrolysable form decreases appreciably with rise in temperature, as expected, due to progressive elimination of the CO_2 -complex with increase in temperature. The adsorption of ammonia as non-hydrolysable nitrogen is, however, seen to increase with the temperature of the treatment. This again indicates that the interaction of charcoal and ammonia (whether in aqueous solution or in gaseous phase) takes place by two distinct processes involving different surface groups.

The adsorption of hydrolysable ammonia, in all probability, is due to presence of the CO_2 -complex; that of non-hydrolysable form cannot be attributed to any other known surface oxygen group, such as quinone, hydroquinone or ether. It may therefore be concluded that another, as yet unidentified group, is responsible for this reaction, which appears to be of activated type as its magnitude increases with rise in temperature.

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